

MULTIMEDIA PLATFORMS AS TOOL OF EDUCATION SYSTEM

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Abstract. *This paper presents the application of multimedia platforms as a key aspect in education process. The great number of requirements, such as privileges and problems of using them in the teaching and learning have led to the research of this nature.*

Keywords: *multimedia platform, teacher, learner, data, education, children, adults.*

Introduction

Nowadays, education is very difficult to imagine without the involvement of technology. Multimedia platforms are one of the most demanded in education. The provided research shows why we need multimedia in the process of teaching and the best uses of it during classes. In addition, what tasks are faced by students and teachers so that this process goes strictly according to the rules and also shows a good consequence at the result of the process.

Multimedia is considered to be a modern computer information technology with the help of which sound, text, video, graphics and animation are combined in a computer system. Thus, multimedia platforms are the ones where these aforementioned functions used. These platforms are good in many ways. For example, for conducting the lessons and gaining knowledge through easy and convenient way. That is mostly because of its online storage. Educational programming, which includes sound, animation and text, is called multimedia programming [5]. Audio, video and animation can have great amount of information. Meanwhile, they can require much space to store them in the platforms.

It is undeniable fact that multimedia platforms provide much data and that it gives the situation where learner manages the work on his or her own, controls the process and does this mostly individually. This means that student is responsible for managing the time, the pace and for the figuring out each step.

Multimedia is an innovation that stands out among other improvements. This interactive media has also influenced the software of the computer system, so that it makes easy for users of those media platforms.

Methods

To date, one of the relevant ways of learning is the use of multimedia technologies. If we turn to the didactic aspects of the phenomenon under consideration, it is appropriate to recall that learning technologies, which are part of social technologies, are understood as “a way of implementing the learning content provided for by curricula, representing a system of forms, methods and means of teaching that ensures the most effective achievement of the set goals” [5, 2].

From a didactic point of view, it can be said that it is a way of teaching the curriculum with the help of new methods of computer technology, which is even considered more effective than other teaching methods. At the same time, there are a number of features that make requirements in almost all disciplines for the demand for multimedia technologies in higher educational

institutions than in others. It is these features that we will consider separately with more details provided.

In universities or higher educational institutions, since students have already been provided with a sufficient amount of knowledge, teachers must prepare materials and a program suitable for them, this is mainly done with extensive information. Thus, students are faced with the task of not only mastering the materials given to them, but also additionally looking for something new. In many cases, students are engaged in the analytical study of volumes of information.

In order to improve the learning process, a multimedia complex was developed for the discipline "Economics", aimed at preparing a full-time form of education for students. It includes lectures and quizzes, interactive books and training simulators for each topic taught. Presentations were made using PowerPoint and iSpringSuit to create electronic resources. In these presentations, there were elements of animation, which greatly helped in mastering the topic [1, 5].

When it comes to children using multimedia platforms, many children find multimedia platforms challenging as many of the activities are done online. However, it is difficult not only for children but also for their teachers, as they are responsible for the whole process and also for the result that they will get at the end. Given that many children have phones with which they can access these platforms, then in general this is not considered a big problem for many teachers, at least from the side of the availability of phones and devices for platforms. Again, their presence is not always a guarantee of high-quality use and understanding of all devices. Despite this, children are those who quickly learn mainly technology and its content.

Thus, if you take the matter seriously, then even if it is not a short time, but maybe if you push it, you will get a result. For this, the teacher should try to work with each child and, if possible, with his parents too. Why parents, because they are responsible for doing homework and making it available on the platforms. As mentioned above, it is a little difficult for children to get used to this system, so if parents look after them, they will immediately learn.

Nevertheless, it is better not to use multimedia platforms with children of elementary grades or immediately from the first grade. This is all because they are still new in the field of learning and immediately using the platforms can discourage them from learning in the future. It has been proven that children can immediately lose their self-esteem and desire to learn.

Adults, on the contrary, like when everything is fast and convenient. The word conveniently means a place and time where the place can be not only an educational institution, but also a home or even work and the word time is understood as any time, not just something specific.

However, it is also worth noting that, if teachers do not control adults, too, then they can also be too lazy and not do tasks on time.

Discussion and Results

The use of multimedia has a number of its advantages, such as: drawing students' attention to the lesson much faster than other information presentations; the presence of visual and audio materials that help the student not only learn information from the teacher, but also see or hear everything for himself; increasing the information provided to students, which they can use not only during classes, but also outside of class time; individual involvement of the student in the classes, since each of them is given basically a separate opportunity to show their skills and knowledge in the field of a particular activity. In the learning process, a special role is played by the independent search of students.

Currently, special attention is paid to how much time the student spends searching for additional information to supplement the information that was provided to them in advance. This is all due to the fact that the modern world is not constant and, in many cases, requires an instant solution of problems and relying on one's knowledge, which will have to be done without any instructions or procedures. In this case, students will have to be provided with some specific ways by the teacher. Universities should help students with the gradual transition to independent education by creating a series of programs or trainings. All this should be along with the development of students' interest in further, more independent search. In the beginning, information should be provided in large quantities, but after some time a gradual reduction should take place so that students already feel responsible for finding the information themselves.

The use of multimedia technologies can help to move from the passive activity of students to a more active one, where the student becomes the main figure who is interested in vocational education. [14]

Conclusion

The above material shows that for the use of multimedia technologies, teachers and students have almost the same responsibility in relation to the learning process, so that the result is satisfactory. Thus, to see a good result, both the teacher and students must work together in cooperation with each other to avoid problems and misunderstandings and achieve the goal in the end. What is more, we must not forget that multimedia platforms are only devices that will help in learning, but they themselves will not show the result if they are not work on and improved.

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